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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL HULAIF M bearing USN 6SU21ML001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA M V bearing USN 6SU21ML002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE RAJENDRAN K bearing USN 6SU21ML003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AYISHATHUL SHAHLA bearing USN 6SU21ML004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DAYANA bearing USN 6SU21ML005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DENWIN DSOUZA bearing USN 6SU21ML006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FARAHATH SAFEEDA S H bearing USN 6SU21ML007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA MUFEEDA bearing USN 6SU21ML008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAWTHAMKRISHNAN A U bearing USN 6SU21ML009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HIBA RAHMAN P K bearing USN 6SU21ML010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JESNA JASEEL M bearing USN 6SU21ML011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms K M ANAGHA bearing USN 6SU21ML012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEGHANA bearing USN 6SU21ML013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED IRSHAD. M.P bearing USN 6SU21ML014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED MUZAMIL bearing USN 6SU21ML015 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NABISHAD MISRIYA K bearing USN 6SU21ML016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDHITHA NARAYANAN bearing USN 6SU21ML017 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms P MOHAMMED AKHEEL bearing USN 6SU21ML018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms POURNAMI K bearing USN 6SU21ML019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RUMANA bearing USN 6SU21ML020 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHYAMA K bearing USN 6SU21ML021 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAISHNAVI NARAYANAN bearing USN 6SU21ML022 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SNEHA RAVEENDRAN bearing USN 6SU21ML023 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAITNA K bearing USN 6SU21ML024 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms YASHODHA RAMESHA GOWDA bearing USN 6SU21ML025 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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